

ISic0203

I.Sicily inscription 0203

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus)

2. Cn(aeus) Octavius

3. Martialis

4. v(ixit) a(nnis) LXXX

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285256

EDR 127471

EDCS 22100129

Bibliography

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Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 126

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